

Relationship between Experiential Avoidance and Depressive Symptoms among University Student

¹Lubaba Shahid, ^{*2}Syeda Anmol Ishtiaq, ³Shamsa Bint Fareed, ⁴Huda Fiaz, ⁵Sobia Arif, ⁶Haseena Ashfaq

¹Students of BS Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

²Students of BS Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

³Students of BS Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

⁴Students of BS Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

⁵Students of BS Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

⁶Lecturer Psychology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh

^{*2}jaffrisayeda@gmail.com

DOI:

Article History

Received on 24 Feb, 2026

Accepted on 28 March, 2026

Published on 30 March, 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Syeda Anmol Ishtiaq

Abstract

Most of the adults who are in their youth group can experience sadness or depression and this is usually associated with ineffective coping mechanisms of unpleasant thoughts and emotions. One of the focal considerations that are currently being studied is the concept of experiential avoidance the tendency to dodge or avoid unpleasant inner events instead of confronting them head-on. This paper identified the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms. It is gathered among 120 female university students aged 18-25 and, therefore, recruited in a convenience sample of a women university. The participants used Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II) to measure level of experiential avoidance and were used to measure level of depressive symptoms using the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). Experiential avoidance was high in 51.7% of the sample indicating that there is prevalence of psychological strain among them. It was also found that 36.7 of the students had moderate symptoms of depressive symptoms, 18.3 moderate levels of depressive symptoms and 5.8 severe levels of depressive symptoms. Experience avoidance was also found to be strongly positively correlated with the presence of depressive symptoms ($r = 0.70$, $p < .001$). It implies that avoidance of our internal experience contributes to depression and it demonstrates the way that therapies based on acceptance such as mindfulness or Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) may become a real difference in preventing and alleviating symptoms of depression. Such results provide a strong framework to begin with mental health professionals, and may assist in the development of better support initiatives among young adults in colleges or universities.

Introduction

Mental health issues are one of the biggest problems of today's generation. According to the reports of World Health Organization (WHO) there are almost 1.1 billion people living with mental health disorders in 2021. According to National Institute of Mental Health there are more or less one in five U.S adults having mental health problems. Mental health is one of the top 10 disorders in 2019 and this is based on the prevalence and global disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) for mental health problems which jumps from 13th to 7th position in few years and show quick rise in global burden (Fan et al., 2025). In Pakistan mental health has become a great challenge because of different taboo's and lack of awareness regarding mental health. Depressive disorder is most noticeable disorder according to different studies containing 3.13% of total DALYs which vary among genders (Alvi et al., 2024).

Several studies have shown that 25 to 35 percent of depressive symptoms worldwide prevalent in university students (Ibrahim et al.,2013; Sarokhani et al., 2013). Depression is a common and serious mental disorder that is different from regular mood changes. It can affect all aspects of life. It is described as prevalent psychological disorder characterized by lack of interest and pleasure, poor concentration, insomnia or hypersomnia, change in weight and appetite, feeling of guilt and worthlessness , fatigue or loss of energy and suicidal ideation or suicide attempts.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2023) reports depression as the leading cause of distress worldwide. High rates of depression can lead to interpersonal conflict, academic decline, and suicide (Bayram & Bilgel, 2008). After such a leading indicator researchers tried to find the causes of depression that what behavior, characteristics and psychological or mental processes can cause it.

It is found that there are so many causes and among that one most important mental construct that cause depression is experiential avoidance. Not only in depression but experiential avoidance found playing role in much other psychological disorder like anxiety disorder. Experiential avoidance is ignorance or avoidance of a person's real emotions, feelings, thoughts and behavior that are distressing (Hayes et al., 1996). According to National Institute of Health (NIH) experiential avoidance refers to a phenomenon in which individuals exhibit an unwillingness to engage with certain personal experiences, including physical sensations, emotions, thoughts, memories, and behavioral tendencies (Wang et al., 2023)

Research Objectives

The main objectives of the study are:

- To measure the prevalence of depressive symptoms among university students
- To examine the level of experiential avoidance among university students
- To determine the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms among university students

Hypothesis

This study tests the following hypothesis:

H1: Depressive symptoms are prevalent among university students.

H2: A significant difference exists in level of experiential avoidance among university students.

H3: Experiential avoidance is positively correlated with depressive symptoms among university students.

Literature Review

Depression is one of the most common mental disorder among university students which effect the academic performance of students, social and occupational and overall quality of life of students (Bayram & Bilgel, 2008). Many students face stress in career uncertainty, academic workload etc. If this stressors not handled well they can lead to emotional disturbance and depression (Eisenberg et al., 2007). Over the past few decades after finding out the disturbance researchers try to find out why some students manage academic stress well and for other students that same problem cause depression and one of the important factor is experiential avoidance which is tendency to avoid unpleasant feelings, negative thoughts emotion and behavior (Hayes et al., 1999).

Depression and Depressive Symptoms

According to DSM 5TR (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (5th ed.,text rev.) depression is diagnosed if there is atleast 5 depressive symptoms is present from past two weeks. In this research we are talking about non-clinical setting, in which depression is the presence of depressive symptoms like lack of happiness or pleasure, insomnia or hypersomnia, eating disturbance lack of confidence and these symptoms interfere with the social and occupational life.

Depressive symptoms are one of the major problems students face in their academic life. Researches have shown that one in three university students throughout the world facing

depressive symptoms (Lei et al., 2016). Studies show that prevalence of depressive symptoms among university students in Pakistan is 42.66% (Jumani, et al., 2023).

Experiential Avoidance

The term experiential avoidance was first explained by Hayes and his colleagues in 1999 in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) framework. It suggests that when a person tries to hide or avoid their inner thoughts, feelings or experiences it will increase his emotional suffering. Experiential avoidance is basically unhealthy or negative coping mechanism a person adopt to regulate his emotions and this process contain try to control or avoid negative feelings, events, thoughts or memories (Hayes et al., 2004).

Experiential Avoidance and Depressive Symptoms

During university life, students face many problems and stress. When they handle stress by avoiding situations and problems instead of addressing them, they might end up on adopting negative coping mechanism like experiential avoidance (Cribb et al., 2012). Experiential avoidance and depression are highly related because both of these involve withdrawal from healthy and meaningful lifestyle. In depression, people often lose interest in activities they once enjoyed . In high experiential avoidance, people leave the situation or places where thy find any kind of discomfort even if the situation is highly significant (Kashdan et al., 2010). This helps to understand why some students can cope with stress while other cannot.

Over the past 15 years, there are lot of researches on experiential avoidance and depression. During this era most studies was built on the foundation of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy and that was to explain how experiential avoidance can cause emotional suffering (Hayes et al., 2011). Researchers find out that EA is not just a coping mechanism but a process plays a key role in mental health issues (Bond et al., 2011).

Researchers also conducted longitudinal studies to understand how EA play a role in depression over time. In a year-long study of Chinese undergraduates, Bai and his colleagues (2022) discovered that EA significantly contributes to depression at various points in time. Pakistan and other Asian nations begin doing serious study on this subject after 2020. Maryam and Khawar investigated EA among college students during the pandemic in 2022 and discovered that it is a strong predictor of academic exhaustion and depression symptoms. This outcome matched the worldwide outcome. Experiential avoidance is now thought to be a major contributing cause to depression (Dixon & Hayes, 2024).

Although there are lots of global researches that confirm the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms but if we try to find out the prevalence of variables in Pakistani culture there is a limited data. And in Azad Kashmir there is no research at all on this topic. So this study was important to find out the prevalence of depressive symptoms and experiential avoidance and their relationship in local population.

Theoretical Framework

This study was based on Acceptance and Commitment Theory (ACT). This theory suggests that negative thinking and emotions are not only the reasons that cause mental health problems but also trying to suppress, hide or avoid negative experiences can cause psychological problems as well. People who rely on experiential avoidance tend to become less flexible and lose touch with activities that matter to them. This can increase emotional distress and make depressive symptoms last longer. In this way, depression is connected to unhealthy ways of handling emotions, especially experiential avoidance. Because of this, ACT is a useful approach for studying how experiential avoidance affects depression in young adults.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design of the study was conducted using quantitative and correlation design in order to find out the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms among university students.

Sample and Sampling Method

The sample consisted of 120 females of age group 18 to 25 enrolled in Women University of AJK Bagh, either in undergraduate or graduate degree program. The sample was recruited using the convenient sampling technique which means that data was collected from the students who were easily accessible and willing to be the part of research.

Instruments

Patient health questionnaire (PHQ-9)

PHQ-9 is a self-report measure designed by Spitzer, Kroenke and Williams to measure the severity of depressive symptoms. It has 9 items that are truly based on DSM-5 criteria for depressive symptoms. People answer each question on a scale from 0 (Not at all) to 3 (Nearly every day) and the total score can be between 0 and 27. All questions count equally toward the total score and there is no reverse scoring or subscales of PHQ-9. Scores from 5 to 9 indicates

mild depression, 10 to 14 moderate depression, 15 to 19 moderately severe depression and 20 to 27 shows severe depression. A score of 10 or higher is often used as a cut-off . Higher scores mean more severe symptoms, while lower scores mean fewer or no symptoms. The PHQ-9 is well known for its reliability and validity in many different groups and settings; it is widely used in both clinical and non-clinical settings.

Acceptance and Action questionnaire II

The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II), devised by Bond and colleagues in 2011; measures psychological inflexibility and experiential avoidance. It has 7 questions, each scored from 1 (never true) to 7 (always true). Higher scores mean more psychological inflexibility and avoidance, while lower scores indicate more flexibility. To get the total score, you add up all items, scores range from 7 to 49. The AAQ-II does not use reverse coding and don't have any subscales. The AAQ-II is reliable tool, with Cronbach's alpha between 0.78 and 0.88, and it has shown good validity in different groups and studies.

Ethical Considerations

Permission was seek from the research committee and Head of department of women university of AJK Bagh. All the information regarding the tools and purpose of the study was given to the participants. Informed consent was taken and confidentiality of the participants was prioritized.

Procedure

After getting the permission, data was collected during the working hours of university. The questionnaires were distributed to the participants with information sheet to give all the required information before giving data. Written consent was also taken. Those who refused to be the part of research were not forced. They were also asked about physical and mental illness. Participants took almost 20 minutes to fill the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS-27. Before analysis data cleaning was performed to remove incomplete and missing responses. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the demographic information and study variables. The reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Pearson correlation was used to find out the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms. For categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were

calculated. For continuous variables, mean, median, mode, standard deviation, Skewness, and kurtosis were used to describe the data distribution and variability

Results

This study was done to explore the relationship between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms among young adults of Bagh AJ&K.

1. Sample Characteristics:

Here are the demographic characteristics of 120 participants.

Table 1: *Frequencies (f) and percentage(%) for demographic characteristics (N=120)*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage(%)</i>
City	Bagh	116	96.7
	Islamabad	1	0.8
	Jehlum	1	0.8
	Rawalakot	2	1.7
Age	(18-21)	87	72.5
	(22-25)	33	27.5
Semester	1	39	32.5
	3	27	22.5
	5	14	11.7
	7	9	7.5
Physical illness diagnosed in present	8	31	25.8
	no	118	98.3
	yes	2	1.7

The first characteristic of the sample was gender, with all participants being female. All participants were also Muslim. Among them, 87 (72.5%) were young adults aged 18 to 21, and 33 (27.5%) were older adults aged 22 to 25. Only 2 participants (1.7%) reported being diagnosed with a physical illness.

2. Depressive Symptoms:

In this study Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)(Spitzer et al., 1999) was used to measure depressive symptoms. Here are the descriptive properties of the questionnaire.

Table 2: *Mean, Median, Mode, Standard Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test statistics of PHQ-9 measuring depressive symptoms*

Scale	M	Median	Mode	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	K-S
PHQ-9	10.89	11	13	5.41	.09	-.40	.07

Note: M=Mean, SD=Standard, K-S= Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

In addition

Figure 1: *Histogram for PHQ-9 scores*

We calculated descriptive statistics for depressive symptoms using the PHQ-9. The average score was 10.89 with a standard deviation of 5.41, and scores ranged from 0 to 24. The PHQ-9 allows for scores between 0 and 27. We checked the distribution of scores for normality. Skewness was 0.09 and kurtosis was -0.40, both within the acceptable range, so the data did not show any major deviation from normality. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was not significant, $d(120) = 0.07$, $p = 0.08$, which also suggests the data did not differ significantly from normality.

3. Experiential Avoidance

Acceptance and Action Questionnaire II (AAQ-II)(Bond et al., 2011) was used to measure EA. Here are the descriptive properties of the scale.

Table 3: *Mean, Median, Mode, Standard Deviation,Skewness, Kurtosis and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test statistics of AAQ-II measuring experiential avoidance.*

Scale	M	Median	Mode	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	K-S
AAQ-II	22.78	23	28	9.02	.23	-.34	.04

Note: M=Mean, SD=Standard, K-S= Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

A histogram was also conducted which support the normal distribution of AAQ-II scores.

Figure 2: Histogram showing the distribution of AAQ-II score.

Descriptive statistics were calculated for psychological flexibility using the AAQ-II. The mean score was 22.78 and the median was 23. Scores ranged from 7 to 45, giving a range of 38. The variance was 81 and the standard deviation was 9.02, which shows moderate variability in the sample. To check normality, skewness, kurtosis, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were used. Skewness was 0.23 and kurtosis was -0.34, both within the normal range, so there was no significant deviation from normality. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was not significant, $D(120) = 0.049$, $p = 0.200$, which confirms the distribution did not differ significantly from normal.

4. Reliabilities of Scales in term of Cronbach's Alpha Reliability (α)

Here are the reliabilities of the scales used in this study.

Table 4: *Reliabilities of Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), and Acceptance and Action Questionnaire II (AAQ-II) in term of Cronbach's alpha reliability (α)*

Scales	N	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness
					Potential	Actual	
PHQ-9	9	10.89	5.41	0.75	0-27	0-24	0.09
AAQ-II	7	22.775	9.02	0.79	7-49	7-45	0.23

The reliabilities of PhQ-9 and AAQ-II were measured using Cronbach's alpha, both scales showed good reliability and validity indicating that both scales were consistent to satisfactory level for use in sample.

5. Prevalence

The following table shows the prevalence of depressive symptoms and EA among university students in AJ&K.

Table 5: *Percentage and frequency (f) for Individuals with minimal, mild, moderate, moderately severe and severe depressive symptoms (N=120)*

Variable	Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Depressive		(f)	%

Symptoms	Minimal	16	13.3
	Mild	31	25.8
	Moderate	44	36.7
	Moderately severe	22	18.3
	Severe	7	5.8

Table 6: *Percentage and frequency (f) for Individuals with high and low EA among university students (N=120)*

Variable	Categories	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Experiential Avoidance	Low EA	58	48.3
	High EA	62	51.7

6. Association of Depressive Symptoms and Experiential Avoidance

Here is the association between the variables

Table 7

Variables	1	2
PHQ-9	---	.695**
AAQ-II	.695**	---

Note: At the 0.01 level (2-tailed) $P < .001$, the correlation is significant.

PHQ-9 and AAQ-II scores showed a high positive connection ($r = .70, p < .001$).

Discussion

This study examine the relationship between experimental avoidance and depressive symptoms among 120 university students. It found 60.8 had moderate to severe depression results show a strong positive correlation ($r = .70, p < .001$) was found the higher level of avoidance of negative thoughts emotions are association with increase depression.(Hayes at al..2011). These findings emphasized targeting experimental avoidance and rumination in therapies like ACT and CBT to reduce depressive symptoms. Aligned with the previous research studies it highlights that depression is a prevalent issue, affecting 25-35% of students globally, and can lead to significant distress, interpersonal conflicts, and academic decline. The research aims to explore this link and understand the role of experiential avoidance in depressive symptoms.

Conclusion

Experiential avoidance is significantly associated with depressive symptoms among university students. Those students who tend to avoid or suppress unpleasant thoughts and emotions are more likely to experience higher level of depression. The result support theoretical models such as Acceptance and Commitment Theory, which emphasize emotional acceptance as a key component of psychological well-being and the emotional suppression lead to depression. The study focuses on the importance of developing acceptance based intervention such as mindfulness and acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT), which help to reduce experiential avoidance and promote mental health. The study concluded that awareness about mental health issues and maladaptive coping techniques like experiential avoidance also help to reduce the level of depression.

Limitations

The study was limited to female participants only so we can't generalize it to the male population. Only young adult students were included in this study. The sample was selected exclusively from Women University of Bagh AJK. The study examines experiential avoidance and the depressive symptoms only without including other psychological variables. This study was limited to convenience sampling; the use of convenience sampling may have impacted the study's generalizability. The study results only apply to particular group of students because there is limited age range (18-25) and small sample size.

Implications

Among young adult female university students, the study discovered a significant positive correlation between experiential avoidance and depressive symptoms, indicating that people who have a tendency to repress or avoid undesirable thoughts and feelings are more likely to have greater levels of depression. Their focus, academic achievement, interpersonal relationships, and general well-being may all suffer as a result. The results emphasize the need for universities to offer helpful programs like mindfulness training and workshops based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), particularly in areas like AJK where mental health facilities are limited. By promoting emotional acceptance rather than avoidance, these programs can assist students in creating healthy coping mechanisms, which will ultimately lessen depression, improve academic performance, and improve overall quality of life.

References

- Alvi MH, Ashraf T, Naz F, et al. Burden of mental disorders by gender in Pakistan: analysis of Global Burden of Disease Study data for 1990–2019. *BJPsych Bulletin*. 2024;48(6):333-340. doi:10.1192/bjb.2023.76
- Bai, X., Wang, Y., & Zhang, L. (2022). Experiential avoidance mediates the relationship between negative emotions and depressive symptoms during COVID-19 lockdown. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 816-828. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.816828>
- Bayram, N., & Bilgel, N. (2008). The prevalence and socio-demographic correlations of depression, anxiety and stress among a group of university students. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 43(8), 667-672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-008-0345-x>
- Bond, F. W., Hayes, S. C., Baer, R. A., Carpenter, K. M., Guenole, N., Orcutt, H. K., Waltz, T., & Zettle, R. D. (2011). Preliminary psychometric properties of the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II: A revised measure of psychological inflexibility and experiential avoidance. *Behaviour Therapy*, 42(4), 676–688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beth.2011.03.007>
- Cribb, G., Moulds, M. L., & Carter, S. (2006). Rumination and experiential avoidance in depression. *Behaviour Change*, 23(3), 165-176 <https://doi.org/10.1375/bech.23.3.165>
- Dixon, M. R., & Hayes, S. C. (2024). Psychological flexibility and experiential avoidance: Contemporary advances in theory and application. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 108, 102-131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2024.102131>
- Eisenberg, D., Gollust, S. E., Golberstein, E., & Hefner, J. L. (2007). Prevalence and correlate of depression, anxiety, and suicidality among university students. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 77(4), 534-542. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0002-9432.77.4.53>
- Fan, Y., Fan, A., Yang, Z. et al. Global burden of mental disorders in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2021: results from the global burden of disease study 2021. *BMC Psychiatry* 25, 486 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-025-06932-y>
- Hayes, S. C., Wilson, K. G., Gifford, E. V., Follette, V. M., & Strosahl, K. (1996). Experiential avoidance and behavioral disorders: A functional dimensional approach to diagnosis and treatment. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 64(6), 1152-1168. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.64.6.1152>

- Hayes, S. C., Strosahl, K. D., & Wilson, K. G. (2011). *Acceptance and Commitment Therapy: The process and practice of mindful change* (2nd ed.). New York: Guilford Press.
- Ibrahim, A. K., Kelly, S. J., Adams, C. E., & Glazebrook, C. (2013). A systematic review of studies of depression prevalence in university students. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 47(3), 391-400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2012.11.015>
- Jumani, S., Osoble, A., Ahmed, T., Rastegarlar, T., Hassan, M., & Sreedharan, J. (2023). Prevalence of Depressive Symptoms Among an Undergraduate Health Sciences Student Population: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus*, 15(8).
- Kashdan, T. B., Barrios, V., Forsyth, J. P., & Steger, M. F. (2006). Experiential avoidance as a generalized psychological vulnerability: Comparisons with coping and emotion regulation strategies. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 44(9), 1301-1320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2005.10.003>
- Maryam, R., & Khawar, R. (2022). Sub-threshold autistic traits as predictor of experiential avoidance and mood states among university students. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(3), 113-120. <https://doi.org/10.52567/pjsr.v4i03.692>
- Wang Y, Tian J, Yang Q. Experiential Avoidance Process Model: A Review of the Mechanism for the Generation and Maintenance of Avoidance Behavior. *Psychiatry Clin Psychopharmacol*. 2024 Jun 1;34(2):179-190. doi: 10.5152/pcp.2024.23777. PMID: 39165887; PMCID: PMC11332439.
- World Health Organization. (2023). Depression fact sheet. WHO. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/depression>